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Returns and Return Policies

The Cost of Coerced Returns in Germany

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Executive Summary

- For policymakers and the public alike, the cost of return migration is an important issue, although it is usually overlooked. Nevertheless, partial data on return costs show that they are expensive and resource-intensive, with direct and indirect costs. Forced removals/deportation are a significantly costly process, depending on the method (by land, by sea, by air) and the destination of the deportee. Although legally, it is not often the responsibility of the state (e.g., Germany) to cover the cost of deportation, however, most deportees lack the financial resources needed to cover such costs, placing the expenses on the government's budget.
- Conducting a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis on return migration seems not to be possible - even at the EU member state level-, because of the lack of comparable data on direct and indirect costs. *Direct costs* include those related to the implementation of return and reintegration programs and deportation's operationalization (e.g., personal, administrative, detention, transportation, escorting, medical assistance etc.). *Indirect costs* extend beyond the visible lines such as the loss of public investment in integrating people who have been ordered to leave, the economic impact of labour shortages and any social effects on the community and individual levels.
- Our stock-taking exercise on Germany's data on returns only provides a limited descriptive analysis, and it shows that the available data are inadequate for a comprehensive analysis of the financial cost-benefits (or trade-offs) on returns. Some fragmented data has been selectively and partly reluctantly provided by German authorities, that provide some incomplete picture about the costs. These include 1) parliamentary inquiries about immigration and return submitted regularly by opposition parties; 2) annual budgetary plans; 3) selective audit reports; 4) sub-titles of national and federal budget lines, and 5) Reports from EU organs, such as Frontex, that indicate Germany's share.
- In Germany, some general rules about data collection are preventing access to a coherent collection of data on returns that might allow conducting a proper cost-benefit analysis. The issue includes
 - The federal system in Germany is characterised by a high degree of legal and institutional complexity. This complexity is especially evident in the multiple rules and regulations for data collection and standards for datasets in the federal states. It also applies to reporting by federal authorities.
 - There are strong legal concerns about the protection of personal data and provisions that limit the use of data to the original purpose for which they were collected.
 - While some inquiries -such as parliamentary questioners- are made regularly and transparently, responses only present data on a certain period and the requested data is unavailable for later dates. Similar problems with time frames of data are present in audit reports as well.
- In Germany, specific data collection and presentation practices about costs related return policies are further complicated by impeding a proper cost-benefit analysis:
 - The budgetary expenses linked to return and reintegration programmes are not tracked at the national level, but rather at the federal state level. Each state operates its own funds, and there is no obligation for a central reporting of such costs. An additional financial computational complication is that some states even run their own return programmes

- Return costs do not appear separately outlined in budgets and are included in budget titles under ‘costs for asylum and integration’. The costs of return data are mostly split across different sources, which risks the error of omission of overcounting biases.
- Direct and indirect return costs (e.g., staff expenditures in the federal police and BAMF and subnational state authorities’ return divisions, and the question of co-financing return measures by Frontex) are difficult to detect with the current available sources.
- The direct financial costs of return migration in Germany are substantial and highly variable. Assisted return and reintegration schemes consume significant resources, while deportations can escalate into extremely expensive operations, especially when long-distance flights and large escort contingents are involved. Each case is individual and accounting for every expense is a difficult undertaking, due to partially shared responsibilities among different authoring involving and high variability in cost. In some cases, the per-person cost of removal reaches several tens of thousands of euros, highlighting how disproportionate expenses can become.
 - The route distance, charter size, and security needs are key drivers of deportation costs. They are often not proportional to the number of people deported. On the low end, there are charter flights to destinations close to Europe, such as Georgia, that carry many returnees with no federal police escorts and an aircraft cost as low as €115,000 (an average per-person cost for such a flight was €2,000). On the other hand, some long or complex operations to countries such as Nigeria or Pakistan cost several hundred thousand euros with many escorts (an example is a flight to Nigeria that cost more than €370,000 and 90 escorts) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). The escort-returnee ratio is often non-fixed, with an escort frequency that usually exceeds the number of deportees (example is a deportation with 26 returnees that required 64 escorts) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). One extreme case was a one-person deportation that required 22 escorts (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025e). The exact cost of employment of such escorts is hard to quantify indeed.
 - One significant component of deportation is related to detention before removal. Aggregate data is not available, only selective data sets for individual years for different (but not all) federal states. Daily rates for individuals in pre-removal detention vary between the different facilities’ location, ownership, joint facility etc.).
- The available (even incomplete) figures illustrate that enforcing return is not only administratively complex but also a major budgetary burden for the German government.

Introduction

Migration governance is at the heart of the political debates in Germany. This is not surprising, given the scale of migration and asylum in recent years and the fiscal implications that accompany it. In 2024 alone, the German federal government's costs for refugees and asylum seekers totalled around €28 billion (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025f, p. 42). The intention to reduce irregular migration has become a major point in both public discussion and political discourse. A central keystone of the debate is the question of return migration, particularly for irregular migrants and rejected asylum seekers. Return—whether assisted (previously so-called voluntary) or coerced—has been framed as a key political instrument in managing migration. This political instrument incurs a cost, so accurate and transparent financial data is crucial for evaluating its cost-effectiveness.

In Germany, the cost of return migration is an important issue for both policymakers and the public, especially since deportation expenses are usually overlooked, including by those most actively pushing for return. Deportation operations have been reported to be extremely expensive, stretching the public budget and raising a lot of questions about their efficiency (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). At the same time, assisted return programmes, though heavily financed by the European Union (EU), still place stress on the Federal States' budgets (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a). These fiscal difficulties are present at a time when political debates present returns as one of the most straightforward and basic solutions to irregular migration. The unspoken reality is that returns – and in particular deportations – are expensive and resource-intensive, with costs that extend beyond the immediate expenditures to economic and societal consequences.

It is essential, before discussing the costs of return, to distinguish between the different types of return, as each carries its own distinct financial implications. Policy distinguishes two categories of return. First is the assisted return, in which migrants co-determine the time of their departure and benefit from logistical and financial support from the state-funded programs. However, these returnees are de-facto forced to leave because their asylum application was either rejected or their temporary right to stay has been revoked for various possible reasons. Second is the case of forced return or deportation in which migrants are removed by force following a legal order due to a rejection of their claim or the expiry, withdrawal, or revocation of a residency title (Mielke et al., 2024, sec. 5.3, pp. 20-22). It is usually associated with higher administrative and security costs (Sahin-Mencütek et al., 2023).

Conducting a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis to answer questions related to return migration costs and support evidence-based decision-making would be appealing, but this is not possible because of the lack of comprehensive comparable data sets (Mielke et al., 2024). The legal and institutional complexity of the federal system in Germany – especially the multiple rules and regulations for data collection and standards for datasets in the federal states and reporting by federal authorities as well as strong legal concerns about the protection of personal data and provisions limiting the use of data to the original purpose for which they were collected – prevents a coherent collection of data on returns that could lead to a unified understanding of facts and figures in the German return regime and inform public debate and decision-making. Additionally, while some inquiries are made regularly, others only cover a certain period, and the requested data is not available for a later date.

While the government refrains from putting together a total cost calculation for ‘refugees’ – this often being the empty signifier for all kinds of measures supported by a budget, including the financing of programmes in origin countries to reduce irregular migration – including direct and indirect costs, i.e. from integration services to infrastructure expansion, return costs do not appear separately outlined in budgets and are included in budget titles under ‘costs for asylum and integration’. Direct and indirect return costs (the latter especially related to staff expenditures in the federal police and BAMF and subnational state authorities’ return divisions, and the question of co-financing return measures by Frontex) are difficult to detect with the current available sources. The costs of return data are mostly split across different sources, which risks the error of omission or overcounting biases.

German authorities only selectively and partly reluctantly provide data on return-related costs. Often, parliamentary inquiries about immigration and return that are regularly submitted by the opposition parties (Mielke et al., 2025) are the only source about costs, annual budgetary plans and selective (but by no means comparable) audit reports complement their partial insights without allowing conclusions about the full picture of spending for sub-titles of national and federal budget lines. From the sources available, it is impossible to link expenditure directly to individuals and project a reliable figure for the costs of return per returnee.

This report attempts a stock-taking in response to the following question: What are the financial, economic, and social costs of return migration -both assisted return and coerced return through deportation- in Germany, and to what extent can these costs be identified and quantified with the currently available data? Due to the multi-layered nature of such costs, a distinction is made between direct and indirect costs. Direct costs - however difficult they are to accurately calculate - would still be possible to measure, while indirect costs are harder to numerically quantify but are no less significant. Direct costs include immediate financial charges associated with implementing return programmes, the administrative, legal, detention and transportation costs associated with deportations. On the other hand, indirect costs extend beyond the visible lines. They include for example, the loss of public investment that has already been made in integration of those receiving a leave-order at some point in time after a long/er period of residence with a temporary right to stay, the economic impact that might result from labour shortages in certain sectors which could be compensated for by training and integrating those who are forced to leave, and any social effects on the community and individual levels.

Direct Financial costs

We begin by examining and providing examples of the direct financial costs, which are the most visible and debated component when it comes to Germany's return policy.

Return and Reintegration Programmes

In Germany, the budgetary expenses linked to return and reintegration programmes are not tracked at the national level, but rather at the federal state level. Each state operates its own funds, and there is no obligation for a central reporting of such costs. An additional financial computational complication is that some states even run their own return programmes (cf. Box 2).

REAG/GARP 2.0 (Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum-Seekers in Germany/Government Assisted Repatriation Programme) is one of the return programmes that offer funds to those who are willing to return to their countries of origin or settle in a third country that shall receive them. REAG funds the returns of those whose asylum application has been rejected, who are in the asylum process or are irregularly residing in Germany, whereas the GARP is for those with a residence permit; in practice, these operate as one programme. Previously run through the International Organization for Migration (IOM), the programme is currently (since January 2024) implemented through the German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) (BAMF, 2025). **The number of recipients of REAG/GARP grants in Germany was 7,872 in 2022 and 10,763 in 2023; facilitated by 648 and 666 eligible bodies (Landeshauptstadt München, 2024, pp. 10, 11). In the year of 2024, it was 10,358 persons (BAMF, 2024).**

Although REAG/GARP explicitly provides the cost items it shall cover (for example: travel costs, medical assistance for the journey, as well as organizational and logistical support), there is no available consistent data on how much was spent through the programme over the years. **A returnee may be given €200 (or €100 for minors) for travel costs, medical assistance may be funded with up to €2.000, as well as a one-time payment of €1.000 per person (or €500 for minors) (REAG/GARP-Programme, n.d.).**

The German Federal government in its response to the parliamentary questions asked in 2025 about the costs of migration answered that the REAG/GARP 2.0 is first financed through **different sources, namely the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) (financing 90% of its costs), the federal government (5% of costs) as well as the federal states themselves (the remaining 5% of costs)**. Among the projected costs are personal and administration costs, which are not easy to account for; an example is that the BAMF staff have already been employed beforehand, and hence the personnel cost can neither be linked nor accounted for as part of return costs (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a). However, it is worth noting that **the budget for BAMF increased considerably over the last years, from €663 million in 2018 to €878 million in 2025 and an expected to be more than one billion euros in 2026** (Bundesrechnungshof, 2025, p. 30). The rationale of this funding increase and extraordinary resource provision in times of tight budgets has been discursively linked to the government's intended decrease ('fight' against irregular migration) of the so-called deportation gap at least since 2015 (ProAsyl, 2024).

Based upon the figures from the answers to parliamentary inquiries by opposition parties for the year 2023, (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a), some figures and categories are as follows:

- For 2024, the implementation of the REAG/GARP 2.0 could roughly amount to more than €300 million for 2024 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a). At the time of the reporting, the

exact values for 2024 were at €490,299.66 and for 2025 at €347,851.31, still to be updated. (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a).

- The financial costs incurred by REAG/GARP were reported to be €11,815,991.36, €12,250,532.14, for the years 2022 and 2023, respectively; these include the personnel and administrative costs, as well as the expenses related to legal proceedings in relation to claims for reimbursement concerning persons who have re-entered Germany (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a, p. 15). These figures only amount to 5% of the full amount spent on the programmes; **the remaining amount is financed through the AMIF fund** that will be explained in the Box 1. (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a).
- One cost category within the programme was investments; an **infrastructure investment** example was provided in the reported answer. Namely, €1,520,361.93 for 2024 and €1,492,336.49 for 2025 were allocated for the adjustment and the operation of **an IT system**
- In 2023, the overall amount was €3,325,267.49 for travel expenses, financial support and coverage of medical expenses, within the framework of the REAG/GARP programme (Deutscher Bundestag, 2024, pp. 2 et seq.). The travel expenses include travel to Germany and to the destination country, as well as any onward travel. In 2022, €2,586,909.56 was spent (ibid).
- Based on the number of funded returnees in the years 2015 to 2023, **an average of €148.30 for travel expenses, €301.70 for financial support and €694.80 for medical costs can be calculated, resulting in a per-person funding of €1,144.80**. It remains unclear whether these expenses are included in the previously named costs incurred by REAG/GARP.
- According to the budget planning for REAG/GARP 2.0 for the years 2024-2026, the total cost was calculated at €85,121,589.71, with AMIF covering 90%, the national budget 5% and the federal states (Länder) 5% (MKJFGFI, 2024) – resulting in an overall expenditure of €4,256,079.49 for both national and federal state budgets together, plus €76,609,430.74 paid by AMIF. This figure was based on the presumption that around 15,000 persons would return each year, covering travel expenses, travel allowances, start allowances, charter flights, COVID costs, services at the airport and special expenditures for vulnerable persons.
- The budget for 2024 was calculated at **€28,057,390.00, resulting in a per-person fee of around €1,900**. These, however, do not include personnel or other administrative expenses.

Box 1. AMIF

The Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) is the European Union's principal funding instrument for 'migration management'; the current funding period lasts from 2021-2027. AMIF supports member states in organising national and subnational asylum, migration, integration, return and readmission processes. Among the objectives of the AMIF are:

- To strengthen and develop the common European Asylum system.
- To promote legal migration and integration of third-country nationals.
- To counter irregular migration and enhance return and reintegration procedures.
- To foster solidarity and responsibility among EU member states.

The total budget for the years 2021-2027 is €9.88 billion for the EU, financed through the general budget of the EU under the Multiannual Financial Framework "Migration and Border Management". AMIF funds are split between national programmes that are implemented

directly by the member states, or thematic facility funds that are used for EU-wide projects (European Commission, 2025). Germany finances 22.6 per cent of the AMIF, and the share it receives out of the AMIF is approximately €1.5 billion for its national programme (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a, p. 6). Many assisted return and reintegration measures in Germany are co-funded by the AMIF (BAMF, 2025), e.g. national revenues resulting from AMIF reimbursements in 2023 amounted to €283.9 million (BMI, 2024, p. 51) and in 2024 to €209.5 million (BMI, 2025, p. 41).

Specifically for return (*Special objective “Contributing to the fight against irregular migration by promoting effective, safe and dignified return and readmission, and contributing to and supporting the first steps towards effective reintegration in third countries”*) €126.4 million was made available for the period 2021 to 2023 (Landeshauptstadt München, 2024). Return projects receive co-financing by AMIF of up to 90 per cent.

StarthilfePlus was introduced in Germany to complement the REAG/GARP programme in 2017. It is an additional assistance programme for those returning “voluntarily”, both rejected asylum seekers and those asylum seekers still in the process of their application but who decide to return. It provides additional financial incentives for return by offering extra cash grants on top of the basic return assistance. The programme is financed through the German national budget and implemented by IOM (BAMF, 2024). Some figures about StarthilfePlus program are as follow:

- The regular support amounts to €1,000 per person, with a maximum funding of €2,000 per family; the reduced support is €400 per person (StarthilfePlus, n.d.).
- The costs incurred by the programme as reported by the German parliament were €12,272,367.61, €10,214,085.51, and €8,527,094.31 for the years 2022, 2023, and 2024. No official figures were provided for the year 2025 at the point of responding to the parliamentary questions (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a).
- In 2024, 4,259 persons received funding through this programme, with a total disbursed amount to recipients of €2,092,060.08, **resulting in a per-person cost of €491.20** (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025c, p. 60). In the first half of the year 2025, 3,445 persons were funded, with a total of €1,416,120.17 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025d, p. 72).

Other return costs incurred by the national budget for subnational programmes like URA 1-2, which is a return and reintegration programme **targeting Kosovan returnees; here, expenses ranged from €351,986.17 in the year 2022 to €628,569.48 in 2025.** The German government also supported the voluntary return of nationals from Syria, Yemen, Libya, Eritrea and Afghanistan, even without their registering in any of the return programmes; e.g., in 2024, the amount of €310,828.56 was allocated for this purpose (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a, p. 16).

Table 1. Cost of National Assisted Return Programs in Germany

Cost of return programmes in euros	2022	2023	2024	2025
REAG/GARP 2.0****	11,815,991.36	12,250,532.14	490,299.66*	347,851.31*
StarthilfePlus	12,272,367.61	10,214,085.51	8,527,094.31	11,144,568.71**
URA	276,942.50	337,861.15	602,987.90***	628,569.48***
Return of nationals from Syria, Yemen, Libya, Eritrea, Afghanistan, without registering via any of the return programmes	202,011.76	221,644.69	310,828.56	228,679.12

Source¹: Deutscher Bundestag (2025). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten René Springer et al. – Drucksache 21/835. [Kosten der Migration in den Jahren von 2022 bis 2025](#). p. 15 et seq.

Some federal states in Germany have also their own programs as Bavaria which will be briefly mentioned in the Box. 2.

Box 2. Bavarian State Return Programme

The Bayerisches Rückkehrprogramm is one example of state-funded return and reintegration programmes that aim to supplement existing national-level return programmes, targeting particular potential ‘voluntary’ returnees residing in Bavaria to increase incentives for ‘voluntary’ returns. The State government of Bavaria allocates substantial funds annually (2021: €904,000; 2022: €695,000; 2023: one million euros; 2024 and 2025: €500,000 respectively) (Bayerischer Landtag, 2024, p. 42). The programme is administered by the Bayerisches Landesamt für Asyl und Rückführung - BLfAR (Bavarian State Office for Asylum and Return). In the words of its President, “Our task is to help ensure that voluntary return to the country of origin is even better supported and that repatriations are carried out even more effectively” (BLfAR, 2023). Individuals who benefit from the State Return Programme can receive funding assistance that cover travel and transport, reintegration aid, subsidies for supporting income generating activities, educational grants, vocational trainings, housing and transportation subsidies, medical assistance and other individual assistance if needed, in total up to €3,000 per person (€1,500 for minors), though the average spending lies at €700 per person (Bayerischer Landtag, 2025). Since the programme’s inception in 2018, 4,485 persons have been supported (as of 30 November 2023) (BLfAR, 2024). While in 2023, 947 persons returned with assistance from the Bavarian Return Programme, the number almost doubled in 2024 to 1,840 returns (BLfAR, 2025).

¹ * the calculated amount as payable by the federal government; ** budget according to the federal financial plan ; *** preliminary; **** These amounts refer exclusively to the contribution by the national government to these programmes, i.e. encompassing only 5% of the total, the rest being contributions from AMIF and the Länder; information for the latter is not given.

Forced Removal/Deportation Expenses

Legally, deportation expenses should not be borne by the government. The costs of deportation are chargeable to the deportee if they have the means to pay. If the returnee was employed, even though under the Residence Act, they were not allowed to pursue an economic activity, the employer is liable for the deportation expenses (Sec. 66 Residence Act). The same applies to persons who committed an offence under Section. 96 Residence Act, namely, smugglers. Authorities are to seize any means that are necessary to cover transport inside and outside of Germany, police escort or any administrative expenses for the preparation and execution of the deportation, including detention and translation, from the employer, smuggler or deportee (BMJ, 2025). In practice, however, most deportees lack the financial resources needed to cover such costs, placing the expenses on the government's budget (ECRE, 2025).

Deportation is a significantly costly process, depending on the method (by land, by sea, by air) and the destination of the deportee. According to the German parliament, **11,807 deportations took place in the first half of the year 2025** (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). The costs of forced return incurred by the German government vary dramatically both by destination and operation type. Additionally, they are often not proportional to the number of people deported. On the low end, there are charter flights to destinations close to Europe, such as Georgia, that carry many returnees with no federal police escorts and an aircraft cost as low as €115,000 (an average per-person cost for such a flight was €2,000). On the other hand, some long or complex operations to countries such as Nigeria or Pakistan cost several hundred thousand euros with many escorts (an example is a flight to Nigeria that cost more than €370,000 and 90 escorts) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). It is also important to note that more than 80% of the deportations mentioned took place via airplanes, with the majority of these deportations operated by Frontex.

Box 3. Frontex

Frontex (the European Border and Coast Guard Agency) is the European Union agency responsible for border management control across the member states. One of the agency's core mandates is to support and coordinate return operations.

- Coordination and organisation of return flights: Frontex organises charter flight removals, coordinates group flights among different states, and provides assistance when using commercial flights for return.
- Support for return processes: Frontex helps member states through the process, starting from identification, organisation of travel documents, transport and escorts, as well as post-arrival assistance. It provides not only technical but also operational and monitoring support.
- Reintegration: Frontex is responsible for the administration of one of the EU reintegration programmes, offering post-return assistance in the countries of origin upon return (Frontex, 2025).

Frontex is funded through the EU budget from member states. Its budget, however, does not only cover return operations but also its international border control activities as well. The 2025 budget shows revenues from the EU and other Schengen member states of more than €1 billion.

Germany's contribution to the Frontex budget is considerable, with 22.5 per cent (€33 billion in 2025 and €30 billion in 2024). Out of the 2024 Frontex budget, around €776 million is dedicated to operational activities, €133 million explicitly for returns – a roughly 33 per cent

increase from the actual confirmed expenditures for returns in 2023, which amounted to €99.2 million (European Union, 2024, p. 3).

The personnel contributions of EU member states for Frontex constitute an additional input that influences member states' own resource bases and capacities. Since 2018, EU member states have had to deploy 1,500 staff to Frontex; recent plans revealed that the build-up of a permanent Standing Corps will lead to 10,000 permanent staff by 2027.

Available figures for Germany's federal police show that it provided 1050 Frontex team members in 2024, who were financed from the EU/ Frontex budget (Bundespolizei, 2024, p 51, 55).

The escort-returnee ratio is often non-fixed, with an escort frequency that usually exceeds the number of deportees (example is a deportation with 26 returnees that required 64 escorts) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b). One extreme case was a one-person deportation that required 22 escorts (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025e). The exact cost of employing such escorts is hard to quantify indeed. Overall, the pattern suggests that the route distance, charter size, and security needs are key drivers of deportation costs.

Another cost associated with deportations is security costs.

- The Federal Government reported incurring €5,609,000 for security escorts for the first half of the year 2025 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025b).
- In 2024, the Ministry of the Interior spent around €9 million on personnel escorting deportations (BMI, 2025).
- For 2026, the federal government budgeted €10.25 million for security escorts (ibid.).

Another significant component of deportation is related to detention before removal. As not all federal states have specialized pre-removal detention centres, some pool capacities, in particular for housing female deportees and/or families. In total, 13 locations existed in 11 federal states at the end of 2024, with a maximum capacity of 800 persons (ECRE, 2025, p. 217). Aggregate data is not available, only selective data sets for individual years for different (but not all) federal states; thus, what follows are example evidences.

- Daily rates for individuals in pre-removal detention vary between the different facilities, e.g., from €455,28 in Darmstadt-Eberstadt (located in and owned by the federal state of Hesse) to €1.523 in Glückstadt (joint facility with 42 places used equally by Hamburg, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern and Schleswig-Holstein, located in Schleswig-Holstein) (Lasarzik, 2024).
- An inquiry in the State parliament of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern about occurring occupation frequency and costs for the accommodation of deportees in Glückstadt shows that it paid €5,520,176.05 for 804 detention days in 2023, e.g., amounting to costs of €6,866 per day (Landtag Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, 2024). According to a complementary source (Landtag Schleswig-Holstein, 2024), Mecklenburg-Vorpommern's share in 2023 amounted to 1,124 days in 2023, which would come down to €4,911 per day. While the 'slim' daily rate in Hesse is calculated as sum of personnel costs, material expenses and the costs of care, accommodation and supplies (Haschnik, 2023), it is plausible that the costs incurred for Mecklenburg-Vorpommern include transportation and other operational and administrative costs. This is corroborated by the fact that Mecklenburg-Vorpommern reimbursed Schleswig-Holstein €2.587.048 in 2023 while it stated to have total expenditures of €5.5 million.

- Given that several federal states have no pre-removal detention facility and many have the intention to increase the detention capacities, several new facilities are being planned. For example, the state government of North Rhine-Westphalia announced in August 2025 to build a second detention centre for 175 occupants in Mönchengladbach nearby Düsseldorf airport, allocating €300 million for this project (Rose, 2025).
- The state of Saxony-Anhalt announced plans to build a 30-persons facility at a cost of €37.4 million (Welt, 2025).

To calculate the total per person cost of a deportation, the different cost factors must be identified. These include administrative cost, such as personnel and material cost in foreigners' authorities, second cost of transportation (flights, train tickets, security escorts) and accommodations cost, namely detention pending deportation, medical cost. However, each case is individual and accounting for every expense is a difficult undertaking, due to partially shared responsibilities and high variability in cost.

The average cost per person of a deportation via charter flight coordinated by Frontex is €7,095 (Statewatch, 2025). Germany received €54 million from Frontex only in 2024, being the recipient of the largest grants (Statewatch, 2025a). Of these €54 million, €28 million were received for deportation operational costs, 19 million for the standing corps and 8.2 million for operational and technical support and deployment (ibid.).

Overall, the direct financial costs of return migration in Germany are substantial and highly variable. Assisted return and reintegration schemes consume significant resources, while deportations can escalate into extremely expensive operations, especially when long-distance flights and large escort contingents are involved. In some cases, the per-person cost of removal reaches several tens of thousands of euros, highlighting how disproportionate expenses can become. These figures illustrate that enforcing return is not only administratively complex but also a major budgetary burden for the German government.

Table 2. The Cost of deportation

Cost of deportation in euros	2022	2023	2024	2025
Security escorts for return	4,183,000.00	6,514,000.00	7,444,000.00	5,609,000.00
Mini-charter flights	no information	1,280,858.00 (number of flights: 15)	272,755.00 (number of flights: 3)	658,090.00 (number of flights: 3)
Charter flights			26,784,120.00	147,479,234.00

Sources: Compiled by authors based on 1) Deutscher Bundestag. (2023). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Clara Bünger et al. – Drucksache 20/5795. Abschiebungen und Ausreisen 2022. p. 19. 2) Deutscher Bundestag. (2024). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Clara Bünger et al. – Drucksache 20/11471. Abschiebungen und Ausreisen 2023 und im ersten Quartal 2024. p. 19-21. 3) Deutscher Bundestag. (2025). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Clara Bünger et al. – Drucksache 20/14946. Abschiebungen und Ausreisen im Jahr 2024. p. 15-17, Anlage 1. 4) Deutscher Bundestag. (2025). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Clara Bünger et al. – Drucksache 21/1239. Abschiebungen und Ausreisen im ersten Halbjahr 2025. p. 14 f., Anlage 1.

Indirect costs

Beyond the immediate direct costs for programmatic support, flights or escorts, return migration also generates a set of indirect costs that, while harder to measure, are still equally important. These include the loss of any investments already made in integration efforts, the economic effects of removing workers from the labour market and the more general social effects borne by society. Unlike direct costs that could be measured and their effects quantified on the immediate or short term, the indirect costs are often diffuse and long-term, yet they are as important in understanding the overall cost of return migration in the German context.

While there is no current method of identifying the costs invested in the sole integration of those who were returned to their countries of origin, whether assisted or coerced, the documentation of rising integration expenditures by both federal and state institutions signals that integration investments are considerable (Bundesrechnungshof, 2022, p. 16). One of the most significant indirect costs of return migration is the loss of public resources already invested in integration measures.

Over the last years, Germany has dedicated substantial funding to help asylum seekers and migrants build the needed language and other skills to integrate into the society. Some figures are as follows.

- Costs for integration measures amounted to €6 billion for the years 2016 to 2021, including integration courses, occupation-oriented German language courses, counselling for adult migrants and other measures for immigrants' integration support (Bundesrechnungshof, 2022, p. 12).
- Between 2022 and 2024, the federal budget for language and integration courses alone has ranged between €586,072,522 in 2022 to €1,233,471.815 in 2024 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025a).
- The total budget for 'refugees and the reception of asylum seekers' was expected to be €21.3 billion in 2024, corresponding to around 5 per cent of the federal government's planned total 2024 expenditure. If the included €7.5 billion for tackling the root causes of migration are deducted, the remaining costs of €13.8 billion for asylum and integration-related expenditures were further composed of social transfer payments after asylum proceedings (€9.6 billion), integration services (€1.8 billion), refugee-related compensation measures for the sub-national level administrative units (€1.3 billion) and costs for reception, registration and accommodation of asylum seekers during the asylum process (€1.1 billion) (Janson, 2024). In the first half of 2025, around €684,219,137 were spent on integration courses, while €1.1 billion has been allocated in the national budget line (established only in the second half of 2025) in total for 2025 (Bundesrechnungshof, 2025, p. 27).

Based on these figures, a rough calculation of how these costs relate to the 3.3 million foreigners with a protection status (asylum seekers, rejected but tolerated asylum seekers, refugees) in Germany in 2024 (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2025) allows the conclusion that the expenditure per person amounts to not more than a four-digit euro amount per person. An EU-wide comparative analysis of the Scientific Services of the German Bundestag found for 2023 that immigrants from non-EU countries receive, with a monthly €410 in Germany, less than in Austria or France (€425 and €426 respectively) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023).

Also, BAMF is charged with payments for integration course providers at the subnational level. While the costs for BAMF staff involved in this type of administration, as well as directly in

the organisation of returns, constitute part of the direct as well as indirect costs of returns, the exact expenditure shares are not quantifiable, as BAMF personnel and operations also deal with asylum, immigration, and return more generally. Overall, the federal government contributed €1.85 billion to the federal states' sub-state administrative units (municipalities, districts) in 2024 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025, p. 4). Expenses covered from these subsidies include the social support expenditures for asylum seekers living in Germany, e.g., for housing allowances, healthcare, welfare benefits and child support. Federal states also finance their own additional services, from housing support to local integration programmes (Deutscher Bundestag, 2024). When a return takes place, especially after several years of residency, much of such funding has already been spent without any foreseeable return to the host society.

Returns may have also negative impact on labour market needs. Germany is currently suffering from sizable labour shortages, which return migration in the long run, risks worsening. As of the first half of 2025, more than 27% of German companies reported the lack of adequate staff levels (KfW, 2025). In high-skilled occupations such as healthcare, engineering, construction and IT, the deficit is even more severe (The Local Germany, 2025). Without (im)migration, such shortfalls might even get more severe, affecting the already ailing German economy. Additionally, the loss of the tax revenues which contribute to the German social insurance system shall constitute a fiscal deficit. Although the majority of returnees are individuals who have no or limited access to the labour market, and thus their tax potentials weigh less in the economic impact calculation at the time being, the potential to integrate asylum seekers and those with impermanent residence status into the labour market in the long term might well constitute a sound basis for filling labour market shortages in the future. Yet, this is another effect that cannot be directly measured.

The impact return has on returnees could be tremendous as discussed in detailed report on Germany-Iraq assisted return schemes (Warda and Al-Obaidi 2026). Returnees frequently suffer from anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorders and depression, more when their departure has been forced or executed under extreme conditions (von Lersner et al., 2008). This not only affects those who have been returned (ed); asylum seekers and refugees living in Germany amid deportations taking place often suffer from uncertainty about their residence status and about anticipated forced removal; moreover, separation from their families also affects their mental health and quality of life (Hajak et al., 2021).

Although the social effects on both the German host society and the individuals are difficult to quantify in monetary terms, they are no less significant and need to be factored into the calculation of overall costs vs. benefits. Any assessment of return that limits itself to financial risks, overlooking these dimensions, will negatively affect the long-term legitimacy of migration policy.

Conclusion

This report has shown that return migration is not a simple, straightforward administrative matter; it is rather a multi-layered process with significant financial and economic implications for Germany. While there is selected data available from parliamentary inquiries and budget plans on the federal level to provide basic insights, they are incomplete and insufficient, lacking the needed details to calculate the exact costs of return in any reliable way (Mielke et al., 2024, sec. 6.4, pp. 45-46). As data on the costs of return are varied and not obtainable from one specific source, the per-person amount spent on returnees cannot be reliably calculated.

Nevertheless, even with those limitations, the evidence shows that the costs of return migration in Germany are substantial. Assisted return and reintegration programmes involve significant allocations from different funding bodies and reach hundreds of millions of euros on an annual basis. While the per-person expense is comparatively low, with just over €1,100 for financial support in 2023, and for 2024 budgeted at around €1,900, with AMIF covering the majority of the expenses. Deportation operations are extremely costly, with a per-returnee cost sometimes reaching tens of thousands of euros. This underlines that return is not only a political issue, but it is also a major fiscal concern. Beyond these measurable costs, indirect costs should be considered as part of the fiscal burden, as the return of migrants often means the loss of public investments for initial integration measures. These figures are even harder to calculate on a per-returnee basis, but the scale of integration investment spent by Germany, namely billions of euros annually, signals that the sunk costs are likely high. Return migration additionally reduces the pool of potential future workforce that Germany needs urgently to remain competitive and cover its employment market needs. The social impact that return – and the politically distorted discourse around it – has on both the public opinion in Germany as well as the psychological well-being of not only those deported but also migrants who remained in the country should not be neglected.

This questions the viability of return as a cornerstone of migration policy. While Germany - not being different from other countries- has emphasised return as a key solution to its migration dilemma, the preliminary evidence presented here suggests that this comes at high costs – both financially, in broader economic terms, and socially. A more balanced approach would be weighing the current costs of enforcing return against the potential long-term contributions of integration. This might be beneficial for the demographic change and the current labour shortage situation in Germany, which will likely worsen. Another key point relates to the return itself; the options at hand should be considered carefully. It is long known (but hardly used to adjust return policy) that assisted return and reintegration is less expensive, not to mention more humane, than forced deportation operations.

In conclusion, return migration cannot be framed as a mere logistical matter; it is a process that involves high financial costs, long-term economic consequences and deep social implications. All these are broadly underestimated and only rarely enter public discourse and inform return policymaking. However, these costs must be weighed before embracing a wide and intensifying return approach. The way forward is not necessarily to increase the funding available for return, but to make the use of the existing resources more transparent, accountable and outcome-oriented. A better cost reporting mechanism, along with nationwide financial tracking, would lay the ground to improve decision-making and inform return policies. Based on the findings in this short analysis, this will likely lead to a greater emphasis

on integration facilitation whenever return is not applicable, with positive effects on social and economic cohesion in Germany.

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